

Appendix C

The course schedule template

Table 1: The course schedule template

Date	Topic	Repository for lab & home activities	Deadline	Lecture notes
dd.mm.yy	Hello R!	soc-datascience-hello	+1w	Welcome to data science! Meet the toolkit: programming Meet the toolkit: version control & collaboration
dd.mm.yy	Data visualization	soc-datascience-viz	+1w	Data and visualisation Visualising data with ggplot2 Visualising numerical data Visualising categorical data
dd.mm.yy	Data wrangling	soc-datascience-wrang	+1w	Tidy data Grammar of data wrangling Working with a single data frame Working with multiple data frames Tidying data
dd.mm.yy	Spatial data	soc-datascience-spatial	+1w	Data types Data classes Data import
dd.mm.yy	Effective data visualization	soc-datascience-reshape	+1w	Data recode Effective data visualization
dd.mm.yy	Simpson's paradox	soc-datascience-paradox	+1w	Scientific studies and confounding Simpson's paradox Doing data science
dd.mm.yy	Collaboration on Github Work on projects	soc-datascience-collabor soc-datascience-project		Web scraping Scraping top 250 movies on IMDB Web scraping considerations
dd.mm.yy	Web scraping	soc-datascience-scrap	+1w	Functions Iteration
dd.mm.yy	Ethics and Data Science	soc-datascience-bias project proposals peer reviews	+1w	Misrepresentation Data privacy Algorithmic bias
dd.mm.yy	Modelling data	soc-datascience-fitting	+1w	The language of models Fitting and interpreting models Modeling non-linear relationships Models with multiple predictors More models with multiple predictors
dd.mm.yy	Classification and model building	soc-datascience-nfitting	+1w	Logistic regression Prediction and overfitting Feature engineering
dd.mm.yy	Model validation	soc-datascience-valid	+1w	Cross validation

Date	Topic	Repository for lab & home activities	Deadline	Lecture notes
dd.mm.yy	Uncertainty quantification	soc-datascience-hypo	+1w	Quantifying uncertainty Bootstrapping Hypothesis testing Inference overview
dd.mm.yy	Text analysis (only lecture notes) Work on projects	soc-datascience-wrapup	+1w	Text analysis Comparing texts Interactive web apps Machine learning
dd.mm.yy	Bayesian inference (only lecture notes)	projects presentations		Interactive data visualization Interactive data visualization and reporting Bayesian inference

Note: See also the project website: <https://the-soc-org.github.io/soc-datascience/>